

Short communication

First record of *Andrallus spinidens* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) for Cyprus

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Abstract. The first record of *Andrallus spinidens* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) for Cyprus is reported. The distribution of the species is summarised.

Key words: Heteroptera, Pentatomidae, distribution, new record, Europe, Mediterranean Region, Cyprus.

Andrallus spinidens (Fabricius, 1787) belongs to the subfamily Asopinae within the family Pentatomidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera), is a non-specific predator on Coleoptera and Lepidoptera larvae, and is considered a potentially useful predator for biological control of crop pests (Manley 1982; Zibae et al. 2020).

It is a large species (12.5 to 16 mm) easily recognisable by its size, pointed and bifid humeral angles of the pronotum, its light brown dorsal colour, and exocoriae with yellowish-white lateral edges.

The species has been reported mainly throughout the Asian intertropical zone, in India, Pakistan and Southeast Asia, between 36° North latitude and 18° South latitude (Cambodia, China, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, to northern Australia), where it probably originated. It was possibly imported to Central Africa (Cameroon, Kenya, Nigeria) and South Africa, and also to the south of the United States, Central America, the north of South America (Colombia), and the Caribbean (Cuba, Dominican Republic, Puerto Rico). It is also found, although more rarely, in the Near East (Egypt, Israel, Syria, Turkey (Anatolia, without specific location)) (Hoberlandt 1995) and in the Middle East (Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Tadjikistan, Turkmenistan, United Arab Emirates) (Péricart 2010; Aukema 2024).

In Europe, it has only been reported in Italy without specifying the locality and in Greece from the west of the Peloponnese (Kaiafas, Nea Manolada) until now (Rieger 2007; Péricart 2010; Aukema 2024).

Now, the first record of *A. spinidens* for Cyprus is reported: on 07.07.2024, an adult specimen was observed and photographed in the city centre of Limassol,

located on the island's south coast. A photograph of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist by a user with the pseudonym “polenodobra”: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/227757484>.

The photo is blurry, but the specimen is undoubtedly identifiable.

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